

Cool Roofs in Northern Ghana: Results from a Pilot Study

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Executive summary

This report shares findings from a pilot study involving a ‘cool roof’ retrofit intervention in the Northern Region of Ghana. In the context of global climate change, Ghana is facing an increasing risk of extreme heat. This poses a threat to education outcomes. Passive cooling interventions—such as painting classroom roofs with reflective white paint to reduce indoor air temperature—offer a potential cost-efficient strategy to adapt existing school infrastructure to mitigate the negative effects of rising temperatures.

The pilot involved two phases of data collection. First, surveys were conducted in 50 primary schools in the Northern Region to map existing school infrastructure and heat-mitigation practices. Second, a difference-in-differences study assessed the impact of a cool roof intervention across 20 classroom blocks, comparing two different paint treatments to unpainted roofs.

Results indicate that a cool roof intervention can reduce temperatures in primary school classrooms in Ghana’s Northern Region, with specialised paint having nearly double the treatment effect of the basic paint (2.21°C vs 1.27°C) and its effect strengthening (compared to control schools) during hours when learning is taking place and the sun is at its strongest. The design of school infrastructure—such as the presence of a ceiling, number of verandas and roof material—did appear to moderate the cooling effect, as did the potential heating effects of an urban environment. A comparison of temperature and relative humidity data between term-time and school vacation dates also suggests that classrooms being occupied diminished the treatment effect.

The discussion focuses on the viability of a cool roof intervention to mitigate extreme heat in Ghana’s Northern Region, the feasibility of its implementation and design implications for future research. While the pilot’s small sample size means all results are provisional, the study aims to provide direction for the focus and scope of future research.

1. Introduction

Ghana is becoming increasingly vulnerable to a range of climatic hazards, such as extreme heat, flooding, and drought ([↑Adelphi & African Union, 2024](#); [↑Desjonquieres et al., 2024](#); [↑World Bank, 2021](#)). This is likely to impact the education sector: flooding and other natural hazards can cause direct damage to schools and disrupt attendance ([↑Mensah et al., 2023](#); [↑Prah et al., 2023](#)), while incremental shifts in climate patterns may disrupt the quality of the school environment ([↑Amankwaa et al., 2025](#); [↑Appah & Koranteng, 2012](#)). Extreme heat is a hazard of particular concern, especially for children’s learning outcomes. Data from 2024 indicates that daily maximum temperatures in Ghana’s northern regions frequently exceed 35°C ([↑D'Rozario et al., 2026](#)), a level shown to reduce academic performance in other contexts ([↑Srivastava et al., 2024](#)).

To mitigate these risks, there is a need for active resilience-building initiatives and evidence-based policy within education systems. One area of resilience-building involves infrastructural adaptations, such as structural changes or retrofits to existing school infrastructure, to make classroom-based learning more resilient to climatic hazards.

This report shares findings from a pilot study involving a ‘cool roof’ retrofit intervention in the Northern Region of Ghana. Following infrastructural surveys in 50 primary schools, 14 school blocks had their roofs painted with reflective white paint, aiming to reduce internal temperatures. Two different ‘cool roof’ retrofit interventions were tested: 7 schools received ‘basic’ white acrylic paint; 7 schools received ‘specialised’ white paint designed for maximum reflectivity on external surfaces; and temperature was measured in a further 6 control schools, which were not painted.

This report presents the context for this research pilot ([Section 2](#)), the methodology ([Section 3](#)), results from the pre-intervention school surveys ([Section 4](#)) and results from the ‘cool roof’ intervention pilot ([Section 5](#)). Given the pilot nature of the study, [Sections 6 and 7](#) discuss the viability of this retrofit intervention as a resilience-building initiative in Ghana and directions for future research.

2. Research context

2.1. Extreme heat in Ghana

With temperatures potentially rising by up to 5.3°C by the end of the century in Ghana ([↑Ghana Meteorological Agency, 2025](#); [↑World Bank, 2021](#)), extreme heat is an increasing risk. An analysis of satellite data by [↑D'Rozario et al. \(2026\)](#) identifies that the northern regions in particular face significant exposure to sustained high temperatures: for nearly a third of 2024 (32.8%), mean regional maximum daily temperatures exceeded 35°C in the Upper West, Upper East, North East, Savannah, Northern Region, and Bono East regions. This analysis is supported by other literature, indicating the significant threat of extreme heat in Ghana's north ([↑Desjonqueres et al., 2024](#); [↑World Bank, 2021](#)).

2.2. The risks of extreme heat for education

Extreme heat has been shown to negatively impact education, with global evidence suggesting that exposure to extreme heat limits learning outcomes ([↑Cho, 2017](#); [↑Graff Zivin et al., 2018](#); [↑Park et al., 2021](#); [↑Srivastava et al., 2024](#); [↑Wargocki et al., 2019](#)). For example, a study in Ethiopia found that 10 days of exposure to temperatures above 33°C can lead to a 2.28% decline in average exam performance ([↑Srivastava et al., 2024](#)), while [↑Park et al. \(2021\)](#) determined that a 1°F increase in temperature across a school year corresponded with an approximate 1% reduction of learning across the same time period. A study of the effects of heat on early childhood development across six countries further suggests that such impacts are heterogeneous, with average monthly temperatures above 32°C having a more severe impact on children from economically disadvantaged households and urban areas ([↑Cuartas et al., 2025](#)).

Classroom infrastructure may exacerbate extreme heat conditions. A study by [↑Pule et al. \(2021\)](#) in South Africa found that indoor classroom temperatures typically exceeded outdoor temperatures by 5°C for 90% of the study period. Similar results were found in Ghana: the indoor temperature of metal-roof classrooms in Accra was 5.9°C higher than comparable outdoor temperatures, equivalent to overheating for 72.5% of occupied hours ([↑Amankwaa et al., 2025](#)). Beyond the impact of higher temperatures on cognitive functioning, this may have indirect effects on other aspects of education. For example, teachers may move lessons to a shaded outdoor location to mitigate the heat; however, this may negatively

impact learning through the comparative lack of learning resources (such as a blackboard or wall displays).

A critical evidence gap on the relationship between extreme heat and education, however, is that most of these studies take place in high-income countries and in different climatic contexts to Ghana—a major issue, considering that extreme heat is projected to affect the poorest regions disproportionately ([↑Venegas Marin et al., 2024](#)). The temperature range examined for its impact on learning is usually significantly lower than average temperatures in Ghana, particularly in the country's north ([↑D'Rozario et al., 2026](#)). One regional analysis of West and Central Africa found that higher temperatures resulted in a decline in average schooling years ([↑Randell & Gray, 2019](#)); outside of this, however, specific evidence pertaining to the impact of extreme heat in Ghana (or similar climatic contexts) on key education indicators is lacking.

2.3. Infrastructural adaptation to mitigate extreme heat

School infrastructure can significantly affect indoor temperatures. A study in Ghana ([↑Amankwaa et al., 2025](#)) highlights the differential impact of different roof materials on classroom temperature: concrete-roofed classrooms were the coolest roof type (especially when outdoor temperatures exceeded 32°C), being up to 5.8°C cooler than metal roofs and, on average, 1.2°C cooler than outdoor temperatures.

While designing new school infrastructure to be climate resilient is a key strategy to mitigating the risks of extreme heat, focus also needs to be given to adapting existing infrastructure—especially in contexts which are most at risk. Critically for Ghana and other low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), any infrastructural adaptation needs to be low-cost to be scalable. This means that many indoor heat-reduction solutions, such as air conditioning, are not viable. Instead, a range of passive cooling mechanisms can be used to reduce extreme temperatures in existing infrastructure. These include: reducing the volume of sunlight to which the building is exposed through additional shading; increasing ventilation; replacing certain building materials; or increasing the amount of sunlight that is reflected. Other infrastructural adaptations may focus on indirectly mitigating the negative impact of extreme heat by targeting other factors linked to children's and teachers' thermal comfort, such as ensuring reliable access to clean drinking water to limit dehydration.

A 'cool roof' intervention is an example of a passive cooling approach that can be retrofitted without major structural adjustments to existing school

infrastructure—potentially a more cost-efficient strategy. It involves painting classroom roofs with white paint to reduce indoor air temperature by increasing the amount of sunlight reflected from the roof.

Non-experimental research indicates the viability of this approach: in Athens, Greece, it resulted in a 1.3–2.3°C reduction in mean indoor temperatures (↑[Androutsopoulos et al., 2017](#)); in Tanzania, it has demonstrated a reduction of 3.7°C over the course of the school day (↑[Proctor, 2022](#)); and in India, an average reduction of 1.5–2.1°C in indoor air temperature was observed over ten weeks (↑[Garg et al., 2016](#)).

2.4. Critical research questions

This pilot study investigates the impact of a cool roof intervention in Ghana’s Northern Region as a strategy to mitigate extreme heat inside lower-primary classrooms. It seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Can a cool roof intervention reduce indoor air temperature in primary school classrooms in northern Ghana?
2. To what extent do existing infrastructural differences between schools impact the effectiveness of a cool roof intervention?
3. To what extent does the impact of a cool roof intervention change across different time periods (i.e., at different times in the day, and on different days in the school year)?
4. Does the type of white paint used impact the effectiveness of a cool roof intervention?

While the pilot nature of this study means that these questions are only exploratory, the aim is to provide an evidence-based foundation for future experimental research and implementation.

3. Methodology

The following methodology received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee for Humanities at the University of Ghana (ref: ECH 118/ 25-26), and research approval was granted by the Director of the Schools and Instructions Division at the Ghana Education Service, on behalf of the Director General. The study was conducted in partnership with DataPlas, a research firm in Ghana.

3.1. School infrastructure and leadership surveys

Surveys were conducted to map existing school infrastructure and heat-mitigation practices at public primary schools in the Northern Region. The objectives of the surveys were threefold:

1. To estimate the level of variation in infrastructure design, quality and heat-mitigation strategies across public primary schools in the Northern Region;
2. To collect data on key variables which affect temperature in the classroom;
3. To assess the viability of the pilot intervention across the sampled schools.

3.1.1. Sampling

Ghana's Northern Region was selected as the site for this pilot study due to the frequency with which this region experiences temperatures which exceed 35°C (see [Section 2.1](#)) and the practical benefits of basing the research in or near the metropolis of Tamale.

To select the final sample of schools, purposive sampling was used to identify two districts that offered a representative sample of rural and urban schools, while also minimising travel for the enumerator and painting teams. The distribution of primary schools designated as 'rural' and 'urban' within each district was analysed using data provided by the Regional Education Directorate. From this, two districts were selected: Tamale Metropolitan, which has the highest proportion of urban primary schools in the Northern Region, and Kumbungu, which has the highest proportion of rural primary schools among districts within an approximate 1-2 hour drive of Tamale.

Probability-proportional-to-size sampling was then used to select 25 urban schools in Tamale Metropolitan and 25 rural schools in Kumbungu. This approach resulted in a representative sample of public primary schools,

weighted by pupil enrolment and distributed across urban and rural locations.

3.1.2. Data collection

Two survey tools were designed and deployed via KoboCollect. The first tool collected data on school infrastructure, including the quality and design of the school roof, classroom block layout and design, and shading levels. Data was collected by a team of enumerators who received a week of training on conducting infrastructural observations and measurements. Since the majority of schools have more than one classroom block, the survey focused on the design and structural integrity of each school's lower primary classroom block.

The second survey tool was designed to be conducted face-to-face with the headteacher of each sampled primary school. Included questions focused on identifying existing heat mitigation strategies and the willingness of school leaders to participate in the pilot (i.e., for their school to receive the intervention).

All 50 infrastructure surveys and 50 school leadership surveys were conducted in the final full week of the first term of the 2025–26 academic year (week commencing 8 December 2025).

3.1.3. Analysis

Survey data was analysed in Google Sheets using descriptive statistics to provide an indication of the variation in infrastructure and heat preparedness of schools in the sample population.

3.2. Pilot cool roof intervention

3.2.1. Assignment of intervention groups

Within each district, sample schools were randomly ordered prior to the surveys and visited sequentially. Sensors were installed in the first 10 schools visited in each district if the school was considered viable for the intervention. Inclusion criteria for sensor installation were:

1. Lower primary classrooms (P1–3) are all in one block (i.e., there is a continuous roof above these classrooms).
2. The lower primary block has walls.
3. The roof is not thatch.

4. The roof is unpainted.
5. The roof is structurally sound.
6. There is no evidence of asbestos.
7. The headteacher/school leader has given consent.

Following sensor installation, the 20 pilot schools were assigned to one of the three intervention groups ('basic paint', 'specialised paint', or 'control'). This assignment aimed to achieve a balanced distribution of the following variables between the three intervention groups (a full overview is available in [Annex A](#)):

- District (Kumbungu or Tamale Metropolitan)
- Roof material (aluminium, aluzinc, or galvanised steel)
- Number of classrooms per lower-primary block (3, 4, or 6)
- Average enrolment per grade (across Primary 1, Primary 2, and Primary 3)
- Average size of each lower primary classroom (square meters).

The final intervention groups comprised: 7 schools receiving basic white paint; 7 schools receiving specialised white paint; 6 schools receiving no paint (i.e., control schools). [Figure 1](#) shows a roof from a school in the 'basic paint' intervention group, pre- and post-intervention.

Figure 1. School roof: pre- and post-intervention ('basic paint')

3.2.2. Intervention design

Paint for the cool roof intervention was sourced from Ghana. Three main exclusion criteria were applied when selecting paint:

1. No alkyd (oil-based) paints, which are less resistant to ultraviolet light ([↑Inspirations Paint, no date](#)) and susceptible to saponification when in contact with zinc ([↑Senkowski & Burgess, 2014](#)).
2. No paint containing lead, due to the health risks associated with lead poisoning, especially for children ([↑UNICEF, no date](#)).
3. No primer containing zinc chromate, due to the associated carcinogenic health risks ([↑Holmes et al., 2010](#)).

Two paints were identified from Ghanaian suppliers: a 'basic' white acrylic paint (Shield Acrylic), and a 'specialised' white paint (Dulux Roofguard), which offers enhanced ultraviolet protection through its Solarflex™ properties. These paints were selected as: a) they were confirmed to be appropriate for exterior, metal roofs; b) the suppliers had enough stock to paint 7 classroom blocks; and c) they offered different levels of reflectivity and emissivity, which would enable a comparison of temperature reduction based on different paint types. The main details of each paint are outlined in [Table 1](#) below.

Table 1. Comparison of cool roof paints used in the pilot

	Basic paint	Specialised paint
Supplier	Azar Paint	Coral Paint
Paint	Shield Acrylic Paint (white)	Dulux Roofguard (white)
Number of coats	2	2
Application	Brush or roller	Brush, roller, or spray
Thinning	Dilute with 10%–15% clean water	No
Technical data sheet	↑Azar Chemical Industries Ltd., 2025	↑Coral-Dulux, 2019
20L unit cost (Ghanaian cedi)	749.80	2357.70
# units per classroom	1.8	1.8
# units per classroom block¹	7.61	7.61

Painting took place from 20 December 2025 to 4 January 2026, during the public school vacations. In line with instructions provided in each paint’s Technical Data Sheet, implementation involved:

- **Surface preparation:** cleaning the roof to remove dust, loose particles, and fatty stains.
- **Primer application:** 1 coat of galvanised iron primer ([↑Coral-Dulux, 2015](#)), left to dry for a minimum of 4 hours.
- **Paint application:** 2 coats of paint within 48 hours of primer application, leaving 4 hours between each coat.

3.2.3. Data collection

Four sensors were installed per school: one in each Primary 1, Primary 2, and Primary 3 classroom (attached to a ceiling beam and out of reach), and one outside in a shaded location (i.e., under a tree or veranda and out of reach). The sensors collected data on temperature (°C) and relative humidity (%) at continuous one-minute intervals.

¹ Assuming an average of 4.23 classrooms per block, based on survey results (see [Section 4.1.1](#)).

The sensors underwent a calibration test prior to installation by analysing data readings over 30 minutes when all sensors were in the same location. As detailed in [Table 2](#), all sensor readings fell within the expected variance (i.e., within the range of the device specifications), suggesting high data accuracy.

Table 2. *Sensor calibration test results*

	Mean	Standard deviation (SD)	Device specifications
Temperature	28.7°C	0.20°C	+/- 0.2°C typical +/- 0.4°C maximum
Relative humidity	34.0%	0.86%	+/- 1.8% typical +/- 3.5% maximum

As presented in [Table 3](#), the pilot timeline included 15 full days of data collection: 7 days pre-intervention (both during and outside of term time) and 8 days post-intervention (during and outside of term time). This equates to 21,600 data units per sensor (i.e., minute-by-minute temperature or relative humidity readings).

Table 3. *Pilot data collection timeline*

	Data type	Dates
Pre-intervention	Term time	15–17 December 2025
	Non-term time (weekend & vacations)	13–14 & 18–19 December 2025
Intervention	N/A (painting)	20 December 2025–4 January 2026
Post-intervention	Non-term time (weekend & vacations)	5–7 & 10–11 January 2026
	Term time	12, 13, & 15 January

3.2.4. Attrition and data errors

The attrition rate for the pilot was 22.5%. This was because, over the full data-collection period, 17 of the 80 sensors were stolen, and 1 sensor was tampered with. As a result, data from 56 sensors was available for analysis for the full period of implementation, with data from an additional 8 sensors available for a reduced period.

Data from the outdoor sensors was then also removed from the final sample due to an error identified with the data. Outdoor sensors had been installed in shaded outdoor locations at ~2m height to act as a

within-school control. However, outdoor sensors, which had been hung under verandas (i.e., the open-air roof overhang outside classroom blocks), were found to have been contaminated by the intervention. As [Table 4](#) shows, the mean outdoor temperature of each intervention group was over 1°C lower than the control during the post-intervention period—a much larger difference than during the pre-intervention period. As a result, these sensors could not serve as a reliable, within-school control.

Satellite data from the ECMWF ERA-5 Land Hourly dataset ([↑Muñoz Sabater et al., 2024](#)) was therefore used as an alternative outdoor control. As [Table 4](#) below also shows, no significant difference in mean outdoor temperature (at ~2m above the ground) was observed between the groups, both pre- and post- intervention. Hence, the satellite data was considered a viable proxy for within-school control measures; however, it is important to note that the data is not site-specific and has a 9km x 9km resolution, so it is not as granular as reliable data from outdoor sensors would have been.

Table 4. Mean outdoor sensor and satellite temperature data (6 am–6 pm), pre- and post-intervention

		Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Intervention group	Mean outdoor temperature	Mean difference (vs control)	Mean outdoor temperature	Mean difference (vs control)
Outdoor sensor data	Control	30.25°C	—	33.37°C	—
	Basic paint	29.65°C	-0.61°C	31.97°C	-1.39°C
	Specialised paint	30.21°C	-0.04°C	32.30°C	-1.07°C
Satellite data	Control	30.88°C	—	30.68°C	—
	Basic paint	30.81°C	-0.07°C	30.66°C	-0.03°C
	Specialised paint	30.93°C	0.05°C	30.75°C	0.06°C

After attrition and data removal, the final dataset comprised 39 sensors over a 15-day period and an additional 6 sensors over a slightly shorter 14-day period: a total of 949,685 individual readings (both temperature and relative humidity). Distribution analysis of the missing and removed sensors indicates a potential bias in the final sample (see [Annex B](#)), as the final dataset is slightly skewed towards rural schools (in Kumbungu) and the intervention groups (with proportionally more data lost from control schools).

3.2.5. Analysis

To test for causal effect, this pilot study adopted a difference-in-differences (DiD) model, comparing the differences in temperature and relative humidity between the control and intervention groups before and after the intervention. This approach was considered appropriate for the pilot data, as it removes fixed differences between the control and treatment groups (thereby isolating the intervention effect from biases caused by fixed variables—i.e., geographic or infrastructural variation between schools) and controls for any time-bound changes (i.e., different times in the day).

A placebo test was first used to check whether the parallel trends assumption was true—i.e., whether, in the absence of the intervention, the differences between the intervention and control groups would have the same trend over time. [Table 5](#) presents the results of four placebo tests. The model assumed that the intervention occurred at midnight on 16 December 2025 (halfway through the actual pre-intervention period). The absence of statistically significant results ($p > 0.05$) indicates no statistically significant deviation from parallel trends in the pre-intervention period and therefore supports the validity of a difference-in-differences model for this pilot study.

Table 5. *Placebo test results*

Intervention groups	Time period	Mean temperature DiD	P-Value
Control vs basic paint	24 hours	0.07°C	0.677
	6 am–6 pm	0.10°C	0.472
Control vs specialised paint	24 hours	-0.01°C	0.972
	6 am–6 pm	0.00°C	0.989

A difference-in-differences analysis was conducted in R (via the ‘fixest’ package), using a two-way fixed-effects linear regression with clustered standard errors and a significance level of 0.05. Classroom-level and hour-date fixed effects were used to control for geographic, infrastructural, and time-related variation. The standard errors were clustered by classroom to avoid autocorrelation. Interactions were added to the model using the ‘i()’ operator, interacting the difference-in-differences estimator with variables including roof material, classroom size, and window type.

The intraclass correlation coefficient was also calculated to compare school-level, classroom-level, and residual variation. This was conducted using a nested linear mixed-effects model (via the ‘lme4’ package) with

temperature as the outcome variable and classroom nested within schools as random intercepts.

Considering the exploratory nature of this pilot study, the results presented in [Section 5](#) should be considered provisional. No a priori power calculation was conducted to determine the sample size, which may result in the study being underpowered and therefore only able to detect relatively large treatment effects. As such, null findings (i.e., non-significant treatment effects) should be interpreted as inconclusive, rather than evidence of no effect.

4. Survey results

Surveys were conducted to map existing school infrastructure (Section 4.1) and heat-mitigation practices (Section 4.2) at public primary schools in the Northern Region. This section first presents the variation in infrastructure in terms of classroom block layout (Section 4.1.1), classroom block roofs (Section 4.1.2) and classroom design (Section 4.1.3); then, results related to school preparedness for extreme weather events (Section 4.2.1) and heat mitigation strategies (Section 4.2.2) are presented.

4.1. School infrastructure²

4.1.1. Classroom block layout

The sampled primary schools had an average of 2.42 classroom blocks (i.e., distinct building structures) per school—a minimum of one block and a maximum of six. According to school leaders, few of the surveyed classroom blocks were built recently; 60% (30 of 50) were over 10 years old.

Considering the financial infeasibility of painting all blocks as part of the pilot intervention, the layout of each school's lower primary classrooms was mapped. As Table 6 shows, lower primary classrooms (Primary 1, Primary 2, and Primary 3) were in the same classroom block in only 74% of surveyed schools (37 of 50). Of these, 46% had multi-level blocks, where the lower and upper primary classrooms sit beneath separate roof structures. Overall, the classroom blocks containing lower primary classrooms had an average of 4.23 classrooms per block. Although in 16% of surveyed schools (8 of 50) a classroom was shared by at least two lower primary grades and in 12% (6 of 5) at least one grade had more than one classroom, 100% of surveyed school leaders (n = 50) stated that lower primary students remained in the same classroom throughout the year.

Table 6. Mapping of lower primary classrooms in surveyed schools

	Yes	No
Are all lower primary classrooms in one building block?	74% (37)	26% (13)
Are P1, P2, and P3 classrooms adjoining each other?	70% (35)	30% (15)
Is the roof above the lower primary classrooms a separate structure to the roof above the upper primary classrooms?	46% (17)	54% (20)

² While surveys took place in 50 schools, a skip logic was applied to some infrastructural observations in instances when the lower primary classrooms were not in the same classroom block (see Section 4.1.1). Hence, the sample size varies between n = 50 and n = 37.

4.1.2. Classroom block roofs

To determine suitability for the pilot intervention and to estimate the level of variation across public primary schools in the Northern Region, information on the composition and structural integrity of existing school roofs was collected. As [Tables 7 and 8](#) show, all surveyed roofs were metal (0% thatch), with galvanised steel the most commonly reported (40.5%); most roofs showed some level of rusting. The majority of roof structures were not observed to contain asbestos (89.2%, 33 of 37) and were not painted (97.3%, 36 of 37)—two requirements for the pilot intervention.

Table 7. *Roof material of surveyed lower primary classroom blocks (n = 37)*

Aluminium	Aluzinc	Galvanised steel	Unsure
21.6% (8)	32.4% (12)	40.5% (15)	5.4% (2)

Table 8. *Proportion of surveyed lower primary classroom block roofs which are rusted (n = 37)*

<25%	25%–50%	>75%	Unsure
67.6% (25)	5.4% (2)	2.7% (1)	24.3% (9)

As presented in [Table 9](#), the vast majority of roofs (98%, 49 of 50) are exposed to direct sunlight—i.e., no significant structures provide shading to the classroom blocks. However, the majority of roofs (98%, 49 of 50) overhang the exterior walls on at least one side of the classroom block to form a veranda ([Table 10](#)), meaning that the roof structures provide some form of shading to the walls, at least during certain hours of the day.

Table 9. *Proportion of surveyed lower primary classroom blocks (n = 50) which are shaded from direct sunlight*

	Yes	No
Does sunlight land on the roof of the primary block?	98% (49)	2% (1)
Does sunlight land on the walls of the primary block?	70% (35)	30% (15)

Table 10. *Proportion of surveyed lower primary classroom blocks (n = 50) which have a veranda*

Yes, a veranda on both sides of the block	Partially, a veranda on only one side of the block	No, the block has no veranda
44% (22)	54% (27)	2% (1)

A majority of surveyed school leaders (60%, 30 of 50) expressed concern about the condition of the current roof of the primary classroom block, mainly due to leaking and age. Just over half of the surveyed roofs (51.4%, 19 of 37) were assessed as at risk of leaking. Nonetheless, 89.2% of the surveyed roofs (33 of 37) were deemed structurally sound and strong enough both to cantilever additional structure and to support the weight of a person. Most school leaders expressed willingness for their schools to participate in the pilot intervention (Table 11), with the main reported concerns relating to roof leaks.

Table 11. School leaders' support for the pilot intervention (n = 50)

	Yes	No	Unsure
Do you have any concerns about painting classroom roofs white?	10% (5)	90% (45)	N/A
Are you willing for your school to be included in the pilot?	94% (47)	4% (2)	2% (1)
Do you have any concerns about installing small temperature sensors in classrooms and/or outside?	4% (2)	98% (48)	N/A
Are you willing for temperature sensors to be installed?	98% (49)	0% (0)	2% (1)

4.1.3. Classroom design

A number of classroom design elements that could affect the impact of a cool roof intervention were examined. Levels of ventilation and direct sunlight were estimated by counting the types and numbers of windows per classroom. As presented in Table 12, the majority of windows were one of three types (also shown in Figure 2 below): design blocks (29%), metal panels (39%), and wood panels (34%).

Table 12. Frequency of window types across surveyed lower primary classrooms (*n* = 105)

Window type	Frequency
Completely open (no covering)	1.9% (2)
Design blocks	28.6% (30)
Lever blade	3.8% (4)
Panel window (metal)	28.6% (30)
Panel window (wood)	34.3% (36)
Sliding/hinged glass	2.9% (3)

Figure 2. Three main window types: (from left to right) design block, metal panels, and wood panels

The majority of classrooms had 4–6 windows (63%), but there was nonetheless a wide range in the number of windows per lower primary classroom (Table 13).

Table 13. Number of windows per lower primary classroom (*n* = 105)

Number of windows per classroom	Frequency
0	2.9% (3)
1–3	27.6% (29)
4–6	62.9% (66)
6–8	3.8% (4)
9–10	2.9% (3)

Floor area was measured due to the potential relationship between classroom size and air temperature (i.e., the larger the classroom, the more indoor air there is to cool). [Table 14](#) shows that classroom areas vary significantly.

Table 14. *Floor size (in square meters) of lower primary classrooms (n = 105)*

Square meterage (sq.m)	Frequency
0–20 sq.m	5.71% (6)
20.01–30 sq.m	12.3% (13)
30.01– 40 sq.m	37.1% (39)
40.01–50 sq.m	21.9% (23)
50.01– 60 sq.m	15.2% (16)
> 60 sq.m	7.6% (8)

4.2. School mitigation strategies

4.2.1. Preparedness for extreme weather events

Of school leaders, 80% reported that some form of extreme weather event had affected their school in the previous academic year. The most prevalent climatic hazard reported was extreme heat ([Table 15](#)), which underpins the importance and appropriateness of assessing the impact of a cool roof intervention as a potential tool for building resilience.

Table 15. *Extreme weather events reported by school leaders to have affected schools in the previous academic year (n = 50)*

Extreme weather event	Yes	No
Extreme heat	64% (32)	36% (18)
Heavy rainfall	28% (14)	72% (36)
Drought	6% (3)	94% (47)
Strong winds	46% (23)	54% (27)
Other	0% (0)	100% (50)
None	20% (10)	80% (40)

When asked to assess their current level of preparedness for extreme weather events, the majority of school leaders (68%, 33 of 50) stated they were “not at all” or “not very prepared”. There was also a reported impact

on education delivery: 30% (15 of 50) reported experiencing at least 1 day of school closure due to extreme weather in the past year (with an average of 4.2 days closed).

To better prepare for these reported climate challenges, school leaders indicated that school infrastructure was the primary area of concern (88%, as shown in [Figure 3](#)). This further suggests that the pilot study is well aligned with existing vulnerabilities and desired actions to support climate resilience.

Figure 3. Perceived support required to prepare schools better for climate challenges, according to school leaders (n = 50)

4.2.2. Heat mitigation strategies

Of school leaders, 24% (12 of 50) reported that lower primary classes sometimes take place outdoors during periods of extreme heat, for a maximum of roughly one day per week. High temperatures were reported as most problematic from February to April (see [Figure 4](#) below).

Figure 4. Months in which high temperatures are perceived to be a problem, according to school leaders (n = 50)

While school leaders of the sampled schools reported adopting a range of other approaches to mitigate the impact of extreme heat (Figure 5), most of these (with the exception of planting trees for shading) were only implemented by a small proportion of schools. This suggests that formal action to mitigate the impact of high temperatures may not be well embedded across public primary schools in Ghana's Northern Region.

Figure 5. Measures taken by schools (as reported by school leaders) to mitigate the impact of extreme heat (n = 50)

5. Cool roof pilot results

5.1. Baseline conditions

Pre-intervention data (from December 2025) was analysed to determine whether any infrastructural differences between classrooms contributed to differences in indoor temperature and relative humidity, before implementation of the cool roof intervention. This section first compares baseline conditions between the three intervention groups ([Section 5.1.1](#)); then, pre-intervention data is disaggregated by district ([Section 5.1.2](#)) and by different infrastructural factors related to roof design, shading, and ventilation ([Section 5.1.3](#)).

5.1.1. Baseline conditions by intervention group

[Table 16](#) presents the pre-intervention average temperature and relative humidity of the classrooms, as well as the average difference between the two intervention groups and the control classrooms. While there was a 0.17/0.18°C difference between control school classrooms and intervention group classrooms pre-intervention, linear regression revealed this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.481$ and 0.477). Likewise, pre-intervention differences in relative humidity between the intervention groups were not statistically significant ($p = 0.671$ and 0.485).

Table 16. *Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor temperature and relative humidity (6 am–6 pm) by intervention group*

Sensor data	Intervention group	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β)	P-Value
Temperature	Control	30.56°C	—	—
	Basic paint	30.36°C	-0.18°C	0.481
	Specialised paint	30.39°C	-0.17°C	0.477
Relative humidity	Control	39.15%	—	—
	Basic paint	39.23%	-0.31%	0.671
	Specialised paint	39.76%	0.61%	0.485

5.1.2. Baseline conditions by district

The sampling strategy for the pilot (see [Sections 3.1.1](#) and [3.2.1](#)) resulted in an even balance of rural and urban schools (from Kumbungu and Tamale Metropolitan districts, respectively). [Table 17](#) presents the average

pre-intervention indoor and outdoor temperatures from each district.³ Results reveal that both indoor classroom and outdoor temperatures in Tamale Metropolitan were hotter than those in Kumbungu to a statistically significant extent. However, the magnitude of the difference was **smaller** indoors, with urban classrooms only half a degree warmer than rural classrooms, compared to over 1.5°C difference between urban and rural outdoor temperatures. While a larger sample size and further research about contributing factors are needed to corroborate the results, this may align with existing research about the heating effect of urbanisation in Ghana (↑Buo et al., 2021; ↑Kwofie et al., 2022; ↑Wemegah et al., 2020).

Table 17. Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor and outdoor temperature (6 am–6 pm) by district

Sensor data	Intervention group	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β)	P-Value ⁴
Indoor temperature	Kumbungu	30.2°C	—	—
	Tamale Metropolitan	30.7°C	0.47°C	0.019
Outdoor temperature	Kumbungu	29.3°C	—	—
	Tamale Metropolitan	31.0°C	1.64°C	0.010

5.1.3. Baseline conditions by infrastructure design

Linear regression of pre-intervention temperature data (see Table 18 below) reveals that, although there was minimal difference between aluminium and aluzinc roofs, the average indoor temperature in classrooms with galvanised steel roofs was 0.40°C higher than in classrooms with aluminium roofs (a statistically significant difference). This suggests that galvanised steel roofs may contribute to higher indoor temperatures when unpainted.

³ Although outdoor sensor data was considered unusable for the difference-in-differences analysis due to contamination by the intervention (see Section 3.2.4), pre-intervention outdoor sensor data was considered reliable.

⁴ Throughout the report, statistically significant results ($p < 0.05$) are indicated in bold.

Table 18. Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor temperature (6 am–6 pm) by roof material

Roof material	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β) vs aluminium	P-Value
Aluminium	30.2°C	—	—
Aluzinc	30.4°C	0.12°C	0.570
Galvanised Steel	30.7°C	0.40°C	0.029

The same approach was used to assess whether having a ceiling affects indoor temperature (see Table 19 below). A statistically significant result ($p = 0.001$) aligns with the findings of a study in Accra by [Amankwaa et al. \(2025\)](#), which suggests that metal-roofed schools with plywood ceilings are cooler than metal-roofed schools without ceilings. Our pilot may support this finding: pre-intervention, classrooms with ceilings were 0.7°C cooler than those without.

Table 19. Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor temperature (6 am–6 pm) by ceiling status

Ceiling present?	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β) vs no ceiling	P-Value
No ceiling	30.5°C	—	—
Ceiling present	29.8°C	-0.70°C	0.001

While classrooms with a veranda on both sides of the classroom block were, on average, 0.25°C cooler than those with only one veranda, this difference was not statistically significant (see Table 20 below). The same was true for window type (see Table 21 below): classrooms with design blocks were 0.12–0.16°C cooler than those with metal or wood panel windows, but this difference was not statistically significant. While these variables are both proxies for classroom shading and ventilation, there may be other factors that significantly contribute to increased/reduced indoor temperatures.

Table 20. Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor temperature (6 am–6 pm) by veranda status

Veranda present?	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β) vs partial veranda	P-Value
Partial (one side of the block)	30.6°C	—	—
Yes (both sides of the block)	30.3°C	-0.25°C	0.200

Table 21. Fixed-effect linear regression of pre-intervention indoor temperature (6 am–6 pm) by window type

Window type	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Difference (β) vs design blocks	P-Value
Design blocks	30.3°C	—	—
Panel window (metal)	30.5°C	0.16°C	0.442
Panel window (wood)	30.4°C	0.12°C	0.491

Linear regression was also conducted to analyse the impact of classroom area (in cubic metres) on pre-intervention indoor temperatures. Results indicate that, for every additional cubic metre of space, classroom temperature increases by 0.002°C. Scaled up, this means a 0.2°C increase in temperature every 100 m³. However, this result was not statistically significant ($p = 0.330$).

5.2. Cool roof impact on classroom temperature

5.2.1. Comparative impact during daylight hours

A difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours⁵ indicates that both the basic and specialised paints had a significant cooling effect, with a greater reduction observed in classrooms in the specialised paint group. Table 22 below presents the results of a two-way fixed-effects linear regression, with an interaction term used to estimate the treatment effect. Although raw mean temperatures rose from December (pre-intervention) to January (post-intervention), both cool roof interventions had a statistically significant cooling effect on indoor temperature relative to the control classrooms when comparing post-intervention to pre-intervention conditions ($p < 0.001$). However, the treatment effect of the specialised paint was nearly double that of the basic paint (2.21°C vs 1.27°C).

⁵ Roughly 6 am to 6 pm during December 2025 and January 2026.

Table 22. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm), including raw mean temperature by intervention group (pre- and post-intervention) and fixed-effects linear regression results*

Intervention group	Mean temperature (pre-intervention)	Mean temperature (post-intervention)	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Control	30.56°C	32.61°C	—	—
Basic paint	30.36°C	31.16°C	-1.27°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint	30.39°C	30.22°C	-2.21°C	< 0.001

The difference-in-differences model was rerun, including satellite data (outdoor temperature at ~2m, see [Section 3.2.4](#)) as a control. As presented in [Table 23](#), this did not change the statistical significance of the results and only marginally altered the treatment effect of the specialised paint.

Table 23. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with satellite outdoor temperature data added as a control to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Basic paint	-1.27°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint	-2.22°C	< 0.001

[Figures 6](#) and [7](#) below present the results of the difference-in-differences model for each intervention group with ‘hour’ included as an interacting variable. This approach visualises the hourly effect of each paint: the blue dotted line represents the treatment effect relative to the control classrooms; the blue shading represents 95% confidence intervals; and any area where the confidence intervals remain below the red dotted line indicates statistical significance.

The results of this analysis provide further evidence of the comparative effectiveness of the specialised paint as a heat-reduction intervention for schools. [Figure 6](#) shows that from around 7 am, the treatment effect of the basic paint begins to diminish; furthermore, the cooling effect of the basic paint compared to control classrooms is no longer statistically significant between approximately 10 am and 2:30 pm. Conversely, [Figure 7](#) indicates that the treatment effect of the specialised paint begins to strengthen from about 9 am until 2 pm, relative to the control classrooms, and is statistically significant throughout the entire 24-hour period.

Figure 6. Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature with 'hour' as an interacting variable, estimating the hourly treatment effect of the basic paint, compared to the control group

Figure 7. Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature with 'hour' as an interacting variable, estimating the hourly treatment effect of the specialised paint, compared to the control group

This is a significant finding, as it indicates a difference in the effectiveness of each paint during the critical period during the day when schools are mostly in session, and daily temperatures are likely to be highest. While the relative cooling advantage of the basic paint diminished compared to the control classrooms as the sun rose overhead, the effect of the specialised paint increased. This indicates that the specialised paint is better suited to dealing with solar radiation and ultraviolet light, especially during times of the day when teachers and learners are in the classroom.

5.2.2. Comparative impact during term time and school vacations

Although the cool roof intervention had a significant cooling effect on indoor temperatures, a differential impact was observed between days when learning was taking place (i.e., classrooms were filled with learners and teachers) and days when classrooms were empty. [Table 24](#) below presents the results of the difference-in-differences model when it was rerun twice, first with temperature readings from term-time dates only, and second with readings from vacation dates only. The results of the two-way fixed-effects linear regression reveal that both paints had a statistically significant cooling effect regardless of the date. However, the treatment effect was almost 1°C stronger compared to control schools during vacation dates than during term time. This may suggest that a cool roof intervention reduces efficiency when classrooms are occupied, as internal heat gains partially offset its impact. However, further research is required to isolate these contributing factors.

Table 24. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during term-time and vacation daylight hours (6 am–6 pm)*

Sensor data	Intervention group	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Term-time dates	Basic paint	-0.83°C	0.002
	Specialised paint	-1.72°C	< 0.001
Vacation dates	Basic paint	-1.70°C	< 0.001
	Specialised paint	-2.65°C	< 0.001

5.2.3. Impact of school-level factors

The intraclass correlation coefficient was calculated at the school and classroom levels (using a nested model) to assess the proportion of total temperature variance attributable to differences between schools ([Table 25](#)). The results suggest that 7% of the overall variance in temperature

occurs between schools—i.e., that school-level factors, such as the geographic location and/or infrastructure of classroom blocks, do have a clustering effect on temperature. The negligible classroom-level intraclass correlation coefficient (explaining 0.5% of variance) indicates that, once you account for which school a classroom is in, room-specific factors had a minimal impact on temperature relative to broader school-wide infrastructure and daily climatic shifts.

Table 25. *School-level and classroom-level intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC), using a nested linear-mixed effects model*

Analysis level	ICC	% temperature variance explained
School level	0.0749	7%
Classroom level	0.0052	0.5%

A difference-in-differences analysis with ‘district’ added as an interaction term in the estimator offered provisional indications of the moderating effect of urbanisation on the cooling effect of a cool roof intervention (see [Table 26](#) below). Both paints were found to have a statistically significant impact on indoor temperature reduction, regardless of district. However, a notable difference was observed in the magnitude of the cooling effect of specialised paint: rural classrooms in Kumbungu were cooled by almost 1.5°C more than urban classrooms in Tamale Metropolitan. Any interpretation of this result is highly provisional, partly because of the sample size and partly because further research is needed to understand the contributing impact of the surrounding environment on classroom temperature. However, considering that pre-intervention data indicates that urban areas are, on average, warmer than rural ones (see [Section 5.1.2](#)), these results may suggest that the impact of a cool roof intervention (which lowers temperatures by reflecting direct sunlight) is diminished by the heating effects of an urban environment, such as proximity to more heat-absorbing materials and the comparative lack of vegetation.

Table 26. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with 'district' added as an interaction term to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Interaction	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Basic paint	Kumbungu	-1.26°C	< 0.001
	Tamale Metropolitan	-1.27°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint	Kumbungu	-2.69°C	< 0.001
	Tamale Metropolitan	-1.24°C	< 0.001

Further difference-in-differences models were then run, adding different infrastructure variables to the two-way fixed-effects linear regression as interactions with the estimator. Table 27 presents the results when 'roof material' was added as an interaction term. Both paints were found to have a statistically significant impact on reducing classroom temperature, regardless of roof material. Notably, the treatment effect of the specialised paint was around 1.0–1.5°C stronger in classrooms with aluminium roofs than those of other roof materials. However, the very small sample size is a strong caveat to this finding, and further testing is needed to explore the relationship between specialised paint and roof type.

Table 27. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with 'roof material' added as an interaction term to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Interaction	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Basic paint	Aluminium	-0.94°C	< 0.001
	Aluzinc	-1.46°C	< 0.001
	Galvanised steel	-1.27°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint	Aluminium	-2.94°C	< 0.001
	Aluzinc	-2.01°C	< 0.001
	Galvanised steel	-1.48°C	< 0.001

A similar analysis was undertaken to examine the interaction between ceilings and the treatment effect (although only for specialised paint, as all classrooms that received basic paint had ceilings and therefore no comparison was possible). While the specialised paint had a statistically significant effect on all classrooms, regardless of ceiling presence, its

cooling effect diminished by approximately 1.6°C if a ceiling was present (Table 28). This result suggests that, while the paint remains effective, its incremental benefit is reduced when ceilings are present, possibly because the additional insulating layer between the roof and the classroom creates a thermal buffer. This aligns with the pre-intervention finding that classrooms with ceilings were already cooler than those without ceilings (see Section 5.1.3), leaving less roof-related heat gain for the paint to mitigate.

Table 28. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with ceiling status added as an interaction to the fixed-effects linear regression model*

Intervention group	Interaction	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Specialised paint	No ceiling	-2.39°C	< 0.001
	Ceiling present	-0.78°C	< 0.001

The pilot also explored the interaction between levels of shading (using ‘veranda status’ as a proxy) with the cooling effect of the two paints. Regression results suggest that, although both types of paint had a statistically significant effect on indoor temperature regardless of veranda status (Table 29), the specialised paint shows a stronger interaction with the degree of shading and coverage. Having verandas on both sides of the classroom block strengthened the treatment effect of the specialised paint by almost 1°C compared to having only one veranda. This may be attributable to a proportionally larger surface area of treated roof: with verandas on both sides, the specialised paint provides a significantly larger reflective barrier. This cumulative benefit was less noticeable for the basic paint.

Table 29. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with ‘veranda status’ added as an interaction term to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Interaction	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Basic paint	Partial (one side of the block)	-1.23°C	< 0.001
	Yes (both sides of the block)	-1.27°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint	Partial (one side of the block)	-1.64°C	< 0.001
	Yes (both sides of the block)	-2.57°C	< 0.001

With respect to ventilation (using window type as a proxy), results suggest that both paint types had a statistically significant effect compared to the control group, regardless of window type (see Table 30 below). While the magnitude of the treatment effect of the basic paint appeared strongest in classrooms with panel windows compared to design blocks, this should be interpreted with caution due to small sample sizes.

Table 30. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with ‘window type’ added as an interaction term to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Interaction	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Basic paint	Design blocks	-1.03°C	< 0.001
	Panel window (metal)	-1.46°C	< 0.001
	Panel window (wood)	-1.28°C	< 0.001
Specialised paint ⁶	Panel window (metal)	-2.17°C	< 0.001
	Panel window (wood)	-2.24°C	< 0.001

Analysis of the impact of classroom area on the treatment effect was mixed (see Table 31 below). While the classroom area did not have a statistically significant impact on indoor temperature compared to control schools pre-intervention ($p = 0.330$, see Section 5.1.3), a significant effect was observed post-intervention ($p = 0.002$). Crucially, however, classroom area did not significantly moderate the cooling effect of white paint: the treatment effect of both basic and specialised paint was statistically significant, but the interaction of classroom area with the

⁶ The dataset did not contain classrooms in both the control group and specialised paint group classrooms that had design blocks, so a difference-in-differences analysis was not possible for this variable.

difference-in-differences estimator was not, indicating that both cool roof paints provide consistent cooling regardless of classroom dimensions.

Table 31. *Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor temperature during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm) with ‘classroom area’ added as an interaction term to the fixed-effects linear regression models*

Intervention group	Interactions	Effect	P-Value
Basic paint	Treatment effect	-1.729°C	0.001
	Classroom area interaction with post-intervention period	-0.007°C	0.002
	Classroom area interaction with DiD estimator	0.003°C	0.262
Specialised paint	Treatment effect	-3.567°C	0.001
	Classroom size interaction with post-intervention period	-0.007°C	0.002
	Classroom area interaction with DiD estimator	0.007°C	0.123

5.3. Cool roof impact on classroom relative humidity

5.3.1. Comparative impact during daylight hours

A difference-in-differences analysis indicates that only the specialised paint had a statistically significant effect on the relative humidity of classrooms during daylight hours (see [Table 32](#) below), although the basic paint approached the significance threshold. Although relative humidity decreased overall from December to January (pre- and post-intervention), both paints appeared to moderate this drying effect, maintaining slightly higher relative humidity (by 1.76% and 2.23%) compared to the control classrooms. A trend towards mid-range relative humidity is a favourable outcome, as this is optimal for thermal comfort.

Table 32. Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor relative humidity during daylight hours (6 am–6 pm), including raw mean relative humidity by intervention group (pre- and post-intervention) and fixed-effects linear regression results

Intervention group	Mean relative humidity (pre-intervention)	Mean relative humidity (post-intervention)	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Control	39.15%	28.42%	—	—
Basic paint	39.23%	29.74%	1.76%	0.055
Specialised paint	39.76%	31.37%	2.23%	0.023

5.3.2. Comparative impact during term time and school vacations

Further difference-in-differences analysis indicates that the cool roof intervention had a differential impact depending on whether the classrooms were occupied. Table 33 presents the results of the model when rerun twice: first with temperature readings from term-time dates only, and second with readings from vacation dates only. The results of the two-way fixed-effect linear regressions reveal that no statistically significant effect was observed during term time for either intervention group; however, during the school vacations, both interventions did have a significant effect on indoor relative humidity, increasing it by over 3.8% and 4.3% compared to control schools.

Table 33. Difference-in-differences analysis of indoor relative humidity during term-time and school vacations daylight hours (6 am–6 pm)

Sensor data	Intervention group	Treatment effect (β)	P-Value
Term-time dates	Basic paint	0.85%	0.374
	Specialised paint	0.83%	0.373
Vacation dates	Basic paint	4.31%	0.003
	Specialised paint	3.86%	0.012

This may suggest that a cool roof intervention has minimal impact on relative humidity when classrooms are occupied, as internal moisture gains likely negate any potential effect during term time. Further research is needed to understand the extent to which this affects learners' and teachers' thermal comfort in particularly hot and arid settings.

6. Discussion

6.1. Viability of a cool roof intervention to mitigate extreme heat in northern Ghana

The pilot results suggest that a cool roof intervention can reduce classroom temperatures in Ghana's Northern Region. Both basic and specialised paint had a statistically significant cooling effect compared to control schools (see [Section 5.2.1](#)). However, specialised paint is considered the more viable for two reasons: first, it demonstrated an almost 1°C stronger cooling effect compared to the basic paint; second, its effect strengthened (compared to control schools) during hours when learning takes place and the sun is at its strongest, whereas the effect of the basic paint diminished (possibly to the point of non-significance, although larger-scale research is required to confirm this).

Notably, the design of existing school infrastructure does, in some instances, appear to moderate the cooling effect of reflective paint. Although provisional due to the small sample size, the pilot results do seem to align with the literature ([†Amankwaa et al., 2025](#); [†Hossain et al., 2026](#); [†Mane, 2024](#)), suggesting that plywood ceilings have a cooling effect on indoor temperature (see [Section 5.1.3](#)). While the cool roof intervention nonetheless had a significant treatment effect, the results suggest that its incremental benefit is reduced by approximately 1.6°C when ceilings are present (see [Section 5.2.3](#)). On the other hand, the presence of verandas on either side of classroom blocks strengthened the treatment effect of the specialised paint (see [Section 5.2.3](#)). This highlights how elements of current school infrastructure may both positively and negatively affect the viability of cool roof interventions as a strategy to reduce classroom temperature.

Three further results, however, caution against the potential effectiveness of a cool roof intervention for mitigating the negative impacts of extreme heat on education. First, the impact of the cool roof intervention was diminished in urban schools, possibly due to proximity to more heat-absorbing materials and the comparative lack of vegetation (see [Section 5.2.3](#)). Second, the treatment effect was diminished by around 0.9°C for both paints when classrooms were occupied, suggesting that its impact may be partially offset by the internal heat gains of a full classroom (see [Section 5.2.2](#)). Third, the impact of the cool roof intervention on relative humidity was negligible, especially during term time (see [Section 5.3](#)).

These results highlight a critical unknown about the impact of a cool roof on thermal comfort. Although temperature reduction was observed, it may not directly improve the thermal comfort of learners and teachers, particularly given the negligible impact on relative humidity. Further research is needed to determine whether a 1–2°C reduction in classroom temperature, when indoor temperatures are already above 30°C, affects children’s thermal comfort, particularly in tropical or semi-arid climates.

A related question about the relationship between indoor temperatures and learning outcomes in northern Ghana remains. Most evidence linking reduced temperatures to benefits for learning and cognitive function comes from much cooler conditions. For example, [↑Park et al.’s \(2021\)](#) study in the United States found that a temperature reduction of 1°C increased learning by 2% for the average student. However, further evidence is needed to establish whether this direct linear relationship transfers into hotter conditions—for instance, does a 2°C reduction from 37°C to 35°C have an impact on learning outcomes in a comparable way to a 2°C reduction from 27°C to 25°C? Key variables, such as hydration, also affect cognitive function and performance ([↑Masento et al., 2014](#)) and therefore would not be addressed in the implementation of a cool roof intervention alone.

As a result, it is yet to be determined ‘how hot is too hot’ for learning in northern Ghana—in other words, the magnitude of indoor temperature reduction required in these conditions for there to be a significant impact on learning outcomes, as well as the temperature range in which these reductions apply, is still unknown. Nonetheless, the pilot clearly identifies that specialised paint has the potential to reduce classroom temperatures, even if further rigorous testing is needed to assess whether that translates into a positive impact for education.

6.2. Feasibility of implementing a cool roof intervention in northern Ghana

The pre-intervention surveys suggest that a cool roof intervention is both a feasible and desired intervention in Ghana’s Northern Region. All surveyed school roofs were metal, with 78.38% eligible for the intervention (i.e., structurally sound, not already painted, not containing asbestos, and with the permission of school leadership; see [Section 4.1.2](#)). Additionally, school leaders reported extreme heat as the most experienced climatic hazard ([Section 4.2.1](#)), with improving school infrastructure the most requested mitigation strategy against future extreme weather disruption (see [Section 4.2.2](#)). This suggests that a cool roof intervention is relevant to both the

majority of existing school infrastructure and the priorities of school leadership; however, it also indicates that structural work may be required for one-fifth of schools in the Northern Region to also be viable for the intervention.

Important questions around the scalability and cost-effectiveness of cool roofs as a retrofit intervention in contexts like Ghana's Northern Region need to be answered. On average, implementing the specialised paint cost GBP 773.25 per classroom for this pilot study (including primer, paint, transportation, fees, etc.), significantly above the cost of the basic paint at GBP 567.44 per classroom. This partly reflects the superior reflectivity of the paint and partly the comparative scarcity of specialised paints in local markets. Nonetheless, paint costs would likely need to be reduced to make the cool roof intervention a cost-effective retrofit.

A related question is about the durability of the cool roof intervention. While retrofit approaches may be less expensive than implementing greater structural changes to schools, their cost-effectiveness depends on how long they remain effective. The structural integrity of the existing school roofs may limit this. In the infrastructure surveys, 51.4% of classroom blocks were reported to have roof leaks, although this was not deemed a reason to exclude them from the pilot intervention ([Section 4.1.2](#)). Leaving such damage unaddressed may affect the effectiveness of the cool roof intervention: any exacerbation of the damage may result in holes large enough for sunlight to bypass the reflective paint, thereby raising indoor temperatures; likewise, exposure to storms and heavy rainfall may cause further damage to roofs, reducing the durability of the intervention.

Future research is therefore needed not just to determine the impact of passive cooling mechanisms (such as roof painting) on learning outcomes in contexts of extreme heat like northern Ghana, but also to investigate the relative cost-effectiveness of a range of different infrastructure interventions. Particular focus should be given to the scalability of the intervention relative to the baseline design and quality of the existing school infrastructure, and to the durability of any intervention, including associated maintenance costs.

6.3. Design implications for future cool roof interventions and research

As discussed in [Section 6.1](#), a clear implication of the pilot is the relative benefits of using a specialised, white reflective paint for any future cool roof intervention. While basic white acrylic paint can nonetheless reduce indoor temperatures (and at a lower cost), its effectiveness diminishes

during peak sunlight and school hours. There may, however, be more to learn about the relationship between different types of paint and roof materials. Although both paints had a statistically significant cooling effect on classroom temperatures across all roof types (see [Section 5.2.3](#)), certain trends in the data suggest this may be an area for further investigation. For instance, specialised paint had a stronger cooling effect of 1.0–1.5°C in classrooms with aluminium roofs than in classrooms with other metal roofs; however, the cooling effect of the basic paint on aluminium-roofed classrooms was around 0.5°C lower than in classrooms with other metal roofs. While these trends are only provisional, considering the small sample size of this study, they may suggest benefits in investigating the thermal mass and thermal conductivity of different metal roof types in relation to different cool roof paint interventions.

Other learnings from this pilot study have implications for future research. For example, the high attrition rate of sensors (22.5%) and contamination of outdoor sensors significantly reduced the sample size (see [Section 3.2.4](#)). This has implications for how indoor and outdoor temperatures are measured in future studies. Human supervision or additional forms of security may be required to ensure that sensor data is not lost in schools in Ghana's Northern Region, which will entail significant additional costs. Finding a suitable outdoor location for sensors is also an unresolved issue: the pilot results indicate that hanging sensors beneath the outdoor veranda leads to a treatment effect; however, there is no consistent alternative for a shaded outdoor area at ~2m elevation, as not all school sites have nearby trees. This raises the question of how best to measure an outdoor comparator or control for indoor sensor measurements.

7. Future research directions

This pilot study provides evidence to support the design and implementation of future cool roof and other passive cooling adaptation approaches in northern Ghana. Given the small sample, the results should be treated as provisional; however, the aim is to inform the focus and scope of future research.

The results suggest that further research would be beneficial in the following areas:

1. The temperature threshold(s) at which learning is negatively affected in Ghana. It is crucial to understand at what temperatures and levels of exposure learning performance is diminished. Determining these specific thresholds is a vital precursor to designing relevant heat-reduction interventions for classrooms in Ghana.

2. The impact of temperature reduction on learners' thermal comfort at different temperature thresholds. While this study found a 1–2°C reduction in classroom temperature following the cool roof intervention, it is unknown to what extent this affected thermal comfort. Establishing this relationship is critical to understanding how temperature reduction might impact cognitive functioning, and to what extent other factors which affect thermal comfort (such as hydration) are key contributors.

3. The cost-effectiveness of a cool roof intervention as a heat-reduction strategy in Ghanaian schools. Once the relationship between temperature reduction and education outcomes is established, a cost-effectiveness analysis is a critical step to understanding the viability of a cool roof intervention compared to other passive cooling retrofits. This should include a comparison with the cost-effectiveness of retrofitting plywood ceilings, which the pilot indicates may be another impactful passive cooling intervention.

4. The thermal mass and conductivity of different metal roofs in relation to cool roof paints. While only provisional, this pilot study may indicate that different white paints have different levels of impact depending on the type of metal roof to which they are applied. Further research is needed to establish the optimal materials depending on existing classroom infrastructure, as well as to establish standards for new school buildings. The evidence base would also be strengthened by comparing such results with the effect of other roof materials and passive cooling interventions on lowering classroom temperature.

5. The scalability and durability of a cool roof intervention in Ghana. The cost-effectiveness of any retrofit likely depends on a) the feasibility of implementing it at scale and b) the duration of its effectiveness. Multi-year research is likely required to identify these factors and understand the extent to which they interact with the impact of a cool roof intervention (both on classroom temperature and learning).

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Annex

Annex A: distribution of intervention schools

Table 34. *Distribution of intervention schools (frequency) pre-attrition and data removal*

		Control	Basic paint	Specialised paint
District	Kumbungu	3	3	4
	Tamale Metropolitan	3	4	3
Roof material	Aluminium	2	2	2
	Aluzinc	2	2	3
	Galvanised steel	2	3	2
Average number of classrooms per block		3.83	4.29	4.29
Average enrolment per lower primary grade		45.11	39.76	37.38
Average classroom size (sq.m)		43.74	43.24	44.41

Annex B: distribution of sensors

Table 35. *Distribution of sensors, pre- and post-attrition/data removal*

		Pre-attrition		Post-attrition/data removal	
		# Sensors	Distribution	# Sensors	Distribution
District	Kumbungu	40	50%	26	57.8%
	Tamale Metropolitan	40	50%	19	42.2%
Intervention group	Control	24	30%	11	24.4%
	Basic paint	28	35%	17	37.8%
	Specialised paint	28	35%	17	37.8%
Roof	Aluminium	24	30%	15	33.3%

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material	Aluzinc	28	35%	15	33.3%
	Galvanised steel	28	35%	15	33.3%
Window type	Design blocks	14	23.3%	12	26.7%
	Panel window (metal)	24	40%	17	37.8%
	Panel window (wood)	22	36.7%	16	35.6%
